

Adversarial Masked Diffusion for Path-Generation Decoupling

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Abstract

Diffusion models usually learn generation and reverse-path construction through the same regression objective. This coupling is stable, but it also makes generation a conditional point-estimation problem: when a corrupted state admits many plausible clean completions, full-sample regression tends to favor averaged solutions. We propose *Adversarial Masked Diffusion* (AMD), a masked diffusion framework for *path-generation decoupling*. In AMD, generation and path formation are assigned to different learning signals: clean-sample generation is learned through adversarial distribution matching, while reverse-path preservation is enforced only through regression on the coordinates that remain visible in the corrupted input. Because generation is handled adversarially rather than by a timestep-specific full regression target, the generator does not require an explicit timestep input; it is used as a shared clean predictor across all reverse steps. The AMD discriminator also receives no timestep embedding, corrupted state, mask, or conditioning image. It receives only a clean-space sample, either a real clean image or a generated clean prediction, and outputs multiple timestep heads. The sampled reverse step selects which discriminator head supplies the adversarial feedback. The masked diffusion process uses nested Bernoulli masks in data space: as the corruption level increases, the set of replaced coordinates grows monotonically, while replacement values are sampled independently at each level. A visible-coordinate path loss anchors the prediction to the unmasked part of the input, preventing the adversarial generator from ignoring the reverse state. Thus, AMD decouples generation from path preservation: adversarial learning matches the clean data distribution, and regression constructs the reverse path.

1 Introduction

Generative modeling can be viewed as the combination of two distinct requirements. The first is *distribution learning*: generated samples should be indistinguishable from samples drawn from the data distribution. The second is *path formation*: when generation is performed through multiple reverse steps, the intermediate states should define a meaningful trajectory from noise to data.

Most diffusion models couple these two requirements into a single regression-based training principle. They prescribe a forward corruption process and train a reverse model with a denoising loss [1, 2, 3]. This provides a stable learning signal for the reverse path, but it also makes the generative component depend on a conditional point-estimation objective. For example, if an x_0 -prediction model is trained with a full-sample squared loss, then the population optimum is the conditional expectation of the clean target given the corrupted input. When the reverse problem is one-to-many, this conditional mean need not itself be a realistic sample. Thus, regression-based generation relies on making each reverse problem sufficiently local, typically by using many small corruption steps and a stochastic reverse update.

Adversarial models take the opposite approach [4]. They directly match generated samples to real data through a discriminator, but they do not by themselves impose a structured multi-step reverse path. This paper studies whether these two roles can be separated. The guiding principle is that generation should be learned as distribution matching, while regression should be used only where the corrupted input provides deterministic path information. If we train a generator adversarially, the most direct objective is to compare generated clean samples with real clean samples. However, if generation proceeds through a diffusion-like reverse chain, the model should not be allowed to ignore the current corrupted state. Thus, adversarial generation and reverse-path construction require different learning signals.

A natural first attempt is to formulate the reverse diffusion process as a sequence of conditional adversarial problems. For example, one may train a discriminator to distinguish real transition pairs (x_t, x_{t+1}) from generated transition pairs (\hat{x}_t, x_{t+1}) . This resembles a conditional GAN formulation of reverse diffusion, and is related in spirit to adversarial denoising approaches that model reverse steps with conditional GANs [5]. However, this approach expands the discriminator’s input space from clean samples to noisy state pairs whose distributions change across timesteps. The discriminator must then spend capacity modeling corrupted conditioning variables and transition compatibility, rather than focusing on clean-sample realism. A noisy marginal discriminator over x_t has a related issue: it still matches corrupted distributions rather than directly matching clean data.

We therefore keep the discriminator on the clean data manifold and make both networks timestep-free at the input level. The generator receives only the current corrupted state and predicts a clean candidate,

$$\hat{x}_0 = G(x_{t+1}).$$

The discriminator receives only a clean-space sample u and outputs one logit per reverse step,

$$D(u) = (D_0(u), \dots, D_{T-1}(u)), \quad s_t(u) = D_t(u).$$

For real samples the adversarial loss uses the t -th head $D_t(x_0)$, and for generated samples it uses $D_t(G(x_{t+1}))$. Thus, t is used to select a discriminator

head, but it is not injected into the generator or into the discriminator backbone as a conditional feature. This gives a direct adversarial signal for clean-sample realism while avoiding networks that are explicitly partitioned into separate timestep-conditioned mappings. However, by itself a clean marginal adversarial objective does not enforce compatibility with the corrupted input x_{t+1} . A generator trained only with this signal could ignore the corrupted state and behave as a path-free adversarial generator.

To restore path structure without turning regression into a full generative objective, we introduce a nested masked path-preservation loss. Under nested masked corruption, some coordinates of x_{t+1} are preserved from the clean sample x_0 , while the remaining coordinates are replaced by noise. The generator is required to preserve only the coordinates that remain unmasked in x_{t+1} . The masked coordinates are not regressed to their paired ground-truth values; they are learned through adversarial distribution matching. During sampling, the mask pattern is nested across reverse steps, but replacement values are level-wise stochastic. A single threshold field determines which coordinates remain masked at each corruption level, and an independent replacement-noise field is used for the target level. Thus, the reverse chain preserves a monotone visibility pattern without carrying the noisy value of a still-masked coordinate from one level to the next.

We call the resulting framework *Adversarial Masked Diffusion* (AMD). AMD decouples path formation from generation. The adversarial objective learns clean-sample realism, while the unmasked-coordinate regression objective preserves the reverse path. This separation avoids two undesirable extremes. With unmasked-coordinate regression alone, the model may preserve the unmasked coordinates but has no direct pressure to generate realistic masked content. With adversarial training alone, the model may generate realistic samples but ignore the corrupted input. AMD combines these complementary objectives so that generation is distribution-driven while path formation is enforced locally through unmasked-coordinate consistency and nested reverse updates.

The contributions of this work are:

- We frame a limitation of full-sample denoising regression as a generation objective: under squared loss, it is a conditional point estimator, so ambiguous reverse problems can favor conditional means rather than distribution matching.
- We propose a path-generation decoupling principle: adversarial learning handles clean-sample generation, while regression is restricted to path preservation on coordinates that are visible in the corrupted input.
- We introduce a masked diffusion process with nested Bernoulli replacement masks, in which the set of noise-replaced coordinates grows monotonically with the corruption level.
- We formulate AMD as a timestep-free adversarial architecture: G takes only x_{t+1} , while D takes only a clean-space sample u and returns multi-head logits $D(u) \in \mathbb{R}^T$.

- We use timestep-head selection $D_t(u)$ instead of injecting t as an intermediate conditioning variable, motivated by the fact that real clean pairs (x_0, t) form the product distribution $p_{\text{data}}(x_0)\pi(t)$.
- We compare against Gaussian-diffusion clean-marginal and conditional-adversarial baselines, including the DDGAN-equivalent $x_t | x_{t+1}$ transition objective.

2 Motivation: Path-Generation Decoupling

A reverse generative model constructs a sample through intermediate states x_T, x_{T-1}, \dots, x_0 , where x_T is a highly corrupted state and x_0 is the final generated sample. The path is useful because it decomposes generation into a sequence of easier steps, but it also imposes a constraint: the final sample should be compatible with the intermediate states used during sampling.

In standard diffusion training, this compatibility is usually learned through a regression objective [2]. Depending on parameterization, the model may predict the clean sample, the added noise, a velocity target, or an equivalent quantity. This is highly effective, but it couples two different roles. The same objective both keeps the reverse chain compatible with the corrupted input and supplies the main learning signal for the generated data distribution.

The issue is clearest for x_0 prediction with squared error. For a full-sample regression loss,

$$\mathbb{E}[\|G(x_{t+1}) - x_0\|_2^2],$$

the population minimizer is

$$G^*(x_{t+1}) = \mathbb{E}[x_0 | x_{t+1}].$$

Thus the regression target is a conditional mean, not a distribution-matching objective. When x_{t+1} admits many plausible clean completions, the conditional mean can average over modes or suppress ambiguous details. This does not mean that diffusion models fail; rather, it explains why regression-based reverse generation benefits from a fine discretization. If each reverse step is small enough, the conditional distribution at each step becomes less ambiguous, and the stochastic reverse update can recover a distribution over samples.

AMD is motivated by removing the generative burden from regression. The clean sample distribution should be learned through distribution matching, so AMD uses a clean x_0 marginal adversarial objective for generation. Regression is retained only where the corrupted input provides unambiguous path information: coordinates that remain visible in the corrupted input should be preserved in the clean prediction. The resulting division is

adversarial clean marginal matching \Rightarrow distributional clean-sample generation,
 visible-coordinate regression \Rightarrow path anchoring.

Adversarial training alone would be path-free, because a generator could ignore x_{t+1} and still match the clean data marginal. Full regression alone would make

clean prediction a conditional point-estimation problem. AMD combines the two while assigning each objective only the role it is suited for.

2.1 Why conditional adversarial diffusion is difficult

The main difficulty with conditional adversarial diffusion is that the discriminator’s input space becomes much larger and more heterogeneous than the clean data manifold. A clean marginal discriminator only receives a clean-space sample and asks whether it looks real. In contrast, a conditional or transition discriminator must also process corrupted states, conditioning variables, or pairs of states whose distributions change with the timestep. This increases the discriminator-side burden: the discriminator must learn clean-sample realism and corruption-dependent compatibility at the same time.

For example, a transition adversarial objective may compare real transition pairs

$$(x_t, x_{t+1})$$

with generated transition pairs

$$(\hat{x}_t, x_{t+1}).$$

If we denote this transition discriminator by $C_t(x_t, x_{t+1})$, its input is no longer a single image from the clean data space. It is a pair in a product space, and the relevant distribution changes across reverse steps:

$$(x_0, x_1), (x_1, x_2), \dots, (x_{T-1}, x_T).$$

The discriminator must therefore allocate capacity to both components of the pair and to the relation between them. As corruption increases, the conditioning state contains more stochastic noise and less clean structure, so the discriminator is asked to model a family of noisy, timestep-dependent pair distributions rather than a single clean real-versus-fake problem.

A conditional clean discriminator has the same input-space issue. One may predict a clean candidate and compare

$$(x_0, x_{t+1})$$

with

$$(\hat{x}_0, x_{t+1}).$$

This avoids judging an adjacent noisy state as the generated object, but a discriminator $C_t(x_0, x_{t+1})$ still receives a clean image together with a corrupted conditioning image. Its input space is again larger than the clean data manifold. The discriminator must use part of its capacity to interpret the noisy conditioning state and to decide whether the clean candidate is compatible with it. For high corruption levels, this compatibility is highly one-to-many, which makes the adversarial task less direct than clean marginal discrimination.

A noisy marginal discriminator over x_t removes the second input, but it still does not keep the discriminator on the clean data manifold. Instead of learning

one clean distribution, it must distinguish real and fake samples across the union of corrupted spaces

$$x_0, x_1, \dots, x_T.$$

For large t , these states contain substantial stochastic noise and are far from the final generative target. Matching such marginals can be useful for a transition model, but it is not the same as directly matching the clean data distribution.

AMD therefore keeps the adversarial discriminator’s input space as small and stable as possible. The AMD discriminator receives only a clean-space sample u , either x_0 or \hat{x}_0 , and outputs timestep heads $D(u) = (D_0(u), \dots, D_{T-1}(u))$. The sampled timestep selects the head $D_t(u)$ after the clean forward pass. Compatibility with the corrupted input is not imposed by giving the discriminator a larger conditional input; it is handled separately by the visible-coordinate path loss.

2.2 Clean marginal adversarial learning

The cleanest adversarial objective is to keep the discriminator on the data manifold. AMD therefore compares real clean samples with generated clean candidates, not noisy states or transition pairs. The generator is a clean predictor

$$\hat{x}_0 = G(x_{t+1}),$$

and the same generator is shared across all corruption levels.

This design is intentionally timestep-free for the generator. At every reverse step, the predicted object is the same type of object: a clean sample in \mathcal{X} . Since generation is handled by the adversarial clean marginal objective rather than by a timestep-specific full regression target, t does not need to define a different output space or a different generator head. The timestep determines how the input x_{t+1} was corrupted and which coordinates are visible for path preservation. We therefore deliberately remove explicit generator timestep conditioning and use a single clean-completion map across all corruption levels. The corruption level remains present through the input statistics and the mask used by the path loss, while stochasticity enters through nested masks and level-wise replacement noise.

The discriminator is also timestep-free at the input level. It receives only a clean-space sample $u \in \mathcal{X}$, where u is either a real clean sample x_0 or a generated clean candidate \hat{x}_0 . The discriminator does not observe x_{t+1} , the mask, or a noisy state. It therefore focuses on clean sample realism rather than on corruption-dependent compatibility. This design deliberately removes the discriminator’s ability to enforce compatibility with x_{t+1} , so the clean marginal adversarial objective must be paired with a separate path-preservation objective.

2.3 Timestep-free discriminator with timestep heads

The clean marginal discriminator also does not receive an explicit timestep input. Instead, it maps a clean-space input to one logit per reverse step:

$$D : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^T, \quad D(u) = (D_0(u), \dots, D_{T-1}(u)).$$

Equivalently, one may write

$$D_k(u) = h_k(f(u)), \quad k = 0, \dots, T - 1,$$

where f is a shared clean-image feature extractor and h_k is the output head for reverse step k . For a sampled timestep t , the adversarial loss uses only the corresponding head:

$$s_t(u) = D_t(u).$$

In implementation this is simply a gather operation on the output vector $D(u)$. No timestep embedding is used inside the network; the training code only indexes the selected head after computing $D(u)$.

This design is natural because all discriminator inputs lie on the clean data manifold. The real clean distribution seen by the discriminator factorizes as

$$p_{\text{real}}(u, t) = p_{\text{data}}(u) \pi(t), \quad u = x_0.$$

Thus every pair (x_0, t) is a valid real clean pair: t indexes which reverse step is being trained, but it does not change the clean-image support. The discriminator can therefore share the same clean-image features across all timesteps and use separate heads only for the final scalar decision.

This clean-pair property is specific to the x_0 marginal objective. If x_t is sampled exactly from the forward corruption process at level t , then (x_t, t) is a valid corrupted marginal sample. However, the target distribution now changes with t , and transition compatibility is stochastic rather than a deterministic sample-level fact. A given x_{t+1} may admit many possible lower-corruption states x_t , and numerically similar corrupted states can arise at different timesteps. Therefore, an arbitrary or model-constructed pair (x_t, t) or (x_t, x_{t+1}, t) is not guaranteed to be a sample from the exact forward marginal or joint distribution unless it is generated by the correct corruption law. In contrast, (x_0, t) is always a valid real clean pair under the clean marginal objective because x_0 and t are independent.

2.4 Unmasked-coordinate path preservation

Path preservation is a local consistency requirement. If a coordinate of x_{t+1} is still unmasked and preserved from the original clean sample, then the clean prediction should preserve that coordinate. If a coordinate has been replaced by noise, the corrupted input does not reveal the paired ground-truth value, and forcing a deterministic target on that coordinate turns an ambiguous completion problem back into conditional regression.

AMD therefore applies regression only to unmasked coordinates. This loss prevents the generator from ignoring the visible part of the corrupted input, while leaving masked coordinates to be learned through adversarial distribution matching. The path loss alone is not a generative objective, and the adversarial loss alone is path-free. Their combination gives the central decoupling principle of AMD:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{clean marginal adversarial learning} &\Rightarrow \text{generation,} \\ \text{unmasked-coordinate regression} &\Rightarrow \text{path preservation.} \end{aligned}$$

The nested sampling rule then turns this local preservation constraint into a coherent reverse path in terms of visibility: coordinates are progressively unmasked according to a shared threshold field. Coordinates that remain masked are not copied from the previous corrupted state; they are assigned target-level replacement noise. Thus, AMD uses nested visibility rather than value-carrying masked noise.

3 Adversarial Masked Diffusion

3.1 Masked diffusion with nested-threshold replacement corruption

Let $x_0 \in \mathcal{X}$ be a clean data sample. AMD defines a replacement schedule $\{p_t\}_{t=0}^T$, where p_t is the marginal probability that a coordinate is replaced by noise at corruption level t . The schedule is chosen before training and satisfies

$$0 = p_0 \leq p_1 \leq \dots \leq p_T = 1.$$

Thus $p_0 = 0$ gives the clean endpoint, while $p_T = 1$ gives the fully corrupted endpoint used to initialize sampling. The exact shape of the schedule is a design choice.

The current AMD implementation uses *nested-threshold Bernoulli masks*. For each coordinate j , sample a single threshold

$$r_j \sim \mathcal{U}[0, 1]$$

and set the level- t mask by the elementwise comparison

$$m_t = (r < p_t).$$

Here $(r < p_t)$ is read as a binary mask with coordinate j equal to one when $r_j < p_t$ and zero otherwise. Because p_t is nondecreasing, the masks are monotone:

$$m_{0,j} \leq m_{1,j} \leq \dots \leq m_{T,j}.$$

Equivalently, once a coordinate is masked as the corruption level increases, it remains masked at all higher corruption levels.

The replacement values are not shared across all levels. Instead, each level has its own coordinate-wise replacement noise,

$$\epsilon_{t,j} \sim p_\epsilon,$$

and the corrupted marginal at level t is

$$x_t = (1 - m_t) \odot x_0 + m_t \odot \epsilon_t.$$

Here $m_{t,j} = 0$ means coordinate j is preserved from x_0 , while $m_{t,j} = 1$ means it is replaced by the level- t noise value. Thus, AMD is nested in the *mask pattern*, not in the replacement-noise value. This distinction matches the implementation: the same random threshold field is used to construct m_t and m_{t+1} , but the noise tensors used at different levels are sampled independently.

For bounded image data represented in $[-\sqrt{3}, \sqrt{3}]$, a simple unit-variance choice is

$$\epsilon_{t,j} \sim \mathcal{U}[-\sqrt{3}, \sqrt{3}].$$

Uniform replacement noise is not essential; other coordinate-wise noise distributions can be used according to the data domain. The essential structure is coordinate-wise replacement with a nested visibility pattern. We refer to the resulting generative process as *masked diffusion*; *replacement* describes the corruption operator, not the method name.

For a pair of adjacent levels used during training, the implementation samples one threshold field r and constructs

$$m_t = (r < p_t), \quad m_{t+1} = (r < p_{t+1}),$$

so that $m_t \leq m_{t+1}$ coordinate-wise. It then samples level-specific noise values and forms, for example,

$$x_{t+1} = (1 - m_{t+1}) \odot x_0 + m_{t+1} \odot \epsilon_{t+1}.$$

When a lower corrupted state is needed for a transition-style diagnostic or baseline, it is formed as

$$x_t = (1 - m_t) \odot x_0 + m_t \odot \epsilon_t,$$

with an independent ϵ_t . The main clean-marginal AMD objective only requires x_{t+1} as the generator input and m_{t+1} for the path loss.

3.2 Training objective

At reverse step t , the generator receives the corrupted state and predicts a clean candidate:

$$\hat{x}_0 = G(x_{t+1}).$$

The generator receives no explicit timestep input. The reverse process remains stochastic because the input states are produced from nested-threshold masks and level-wise coordinate replacement noise. The timestep still determines the

corruption distribution used to draw x_{t+1} and the mask used in the path loss, but it is not an input to G .

AMD uses a timestep-free multi-head clean marginal discriminator

$$D(u) = (D_0(u), \dots, D_{T-1}(u)).$$

The discriminator forward pass is always on a clean-space sample only: $D(x_0)$ for a real sample and $D(\hat{x}_0)$ for a generated clean prediction. It is not conditioned on x_{t+1} , does not observe the mask, and does not receive t as a network input. The sampled timestep is used only after the forward pass to select the corresponding output head. Since the real discriminator input is always clean, real pairs are drawn as (x_0, t) with $x_0 \sim p_{\text{data}}$ and $t \sim \pi(t)$ independently. For a sampled timestep, the adversarial losses use the selected head directly:

$$L_D = \ell_D(D_t(x_0), D_t(\hat{x}_0)),$$

$$L_G^{\text{adv}} = \ell_G(D_t(\hat{x}_0)).$$

The implementation may compute the full vector $D(u)$ and gather its t -th component. This selection happens after the clean-input discriminator forward pass; t is not a feature-conditioning input. The notation above keeps AMD independent of the particular GAN objective: logistic, hinge, Wasserstein-style, or other adversarial losses can be used. Any discriminator-side regularization can be included inside ℓ_D .

The unmasked-coordinate path loss is applied only where the corrupted input still contains clean information:

$$L_{\text{path}} = \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{d_x} \|(1 - m_{t+1}) \odot (\hat{x}_0 - x_0)\|_2^2 \right].$$

This matches the implementation in which masked coordinates are zeroed out and the result is averaged over the full data dimension d_x . Thus, the loss preserves unmasked coordinates without normalizing away the number of unmasked coordinates at a given corruption level.

The full generator objective fixes the adversarial coefficient to one and weights only the path term:

$$L_G = L_G^{\text{adv}} + \lambda_{\text{path}} L_{\text{path}}.$$

Regression is therefore restricted to path preservation, while adversarial learning is responsible for clean-sample realism.

3.3 Training algorithm

For each minibatch, we sample a clean example x_0 , a timestep $t \in \{0, \dots, T-1\}$, a nested threshold field, and level- $(t+1)$ coordinate-wise replacement noise. The corrupted input is

$$x_{t+1} = (1 - m_{t+1}) \odot x_0 + m_{t+1} \odot \epsilon_{t+1}.$$

The generator predicts $\hat{x}_0 = G(x_{t+1})$. The discriminator maps each clean input to T timestep heads, and the adversarial loss gathers the head indexed by the sampled timestep t . In particular, the discriminator calls are $D(x_0)$ and $D(\hat{x}_0)$, followed by selecting the t -th head. The discriminator does not receive x_{t+1} , the mask, or a noisy state, and t is not injected into its features. Algorithm 1 summarizes the training procedure.

Algorithm 1 Training AMD with nested-threshold masks

Require: Data distribution p_{data}

Require: Timestep-free generator G , timestep-free multi-head discriminator $D : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^T$

Require: Replacement schedule $\{p_t\}_{t=0}^T$, with $0 = p_0 \leq \dots \leq p_T = 1$

Require: Coordinate-wise noise distribution p_ϵ

Require: Path-loss weight λ_{path}

1: Initialize G and D

2: **while** not converged **do**

Discriminator update

3: Sample $x_0 \sim p_{\text{data}}$ and $t \in \{0, \dots, T-1\}$

4: Sample nested threshold field and level- $(t+1)$ replacement noise

$$r_j \sim \mathcal{U}[0, 1], \quad \epsilon_{t+1,j} \sim p_\epsilon$$

5: Set nested mask $m_{t+1} = (r < p_{t+1})$

6: Construct corrupted input

$$x_{t+1} = (1 - m_{t+1}) \odot x_0 + m_{t+1} \odot \epsilon_{t+1}$$

7: Generate $\hat{x}_0 = G(x_{t+1})$ with G fixed

8: Compute discriminator loss using the timestep head t

$$L_D = \ell_D(D_t(x_0), D_t(\hat{x}_0))$$

9: Update D by descending L_D

Generator update

10: Sample $x_0 \sim p_{\text{data}}$ and $t \in \{0, \dots, T-1\}$

11: Sample nested threshold field and level- $(t+1)$ replacement noise

$$r_j \sim \mathcal{U}[0, 1], \quad \epsilon_{t+1,j} \sim p_\epsilon$$

12: Set nested mask $m_{t+1} = (r < p_{t+1})$

13: Construct corrupted input

$$x_{t+1} = (1 - m_{t+1}) \odot x_0 + m_{t+1} \odot \epsilon_{t+1}$$

14: Predict $\hat{x}_0 = G(x_{t+1})$

15: Compute generator adversarial loss using the timestep head t

$$L_G^{\text{adv}} = \ell_G(D_t(\hat{x}_0))$$

16: Compute unmasked-coordinate path loss

$$L_{\text{path}} = \frac{1}{d_x} \|(1 - m_{t+1}) \odot (\hat{x}_0 - x_0)\|_2^2$$

17: Compute generator loss

$$L_G = L_G^{\text{adv}} + \lambda_{\text{path}} L_{\text{path}}$$

18: Update G by descending L_G

19: **end while**

3.4 Sampling algorithm

Sampling starts from a fully corrupted state. Since $p_T = 1$, the initial state contains no clean data coordinates, so we sample

$$x_{T,j} \sim p_\epsilon.$$

We also sample a threshold field $r_j \sim \mathcal{U}[0, 1]$, which fixes the nested mask pattern used across the reverse chain, and independent replacement-noise tensors ϵ_t for the target levels $t = 0, \dots, T - 1$. We then run the reverse chain from $t = T - 1$ down to 0. At each step, the generator predicts a clean sample from the current corrupted state, and the next lower-corruption state is constructed using the nested target mask $m_t = (r < p_t)$ and the level- t replacement noise.

Algorithm 2 Sampling AMD with nested-threshold masks

Require: Trained timestep-free generator G

Require: Replacement schedule $\{p_t\}_{t=0}^T$, with $0 = p_0 \leq \dots \leq p_T = 1$

Require: Coordinate-wise noise distribution p_ϵ

1: Sample initial corrupted state

$$x_{T,j} \sim p_\epsilon$$

2: Sample a threshold field

$$r_j \sim \mathcal{U}[0, 1]$$

3: Sample level-wise replacement noise for $t = 0, \dots, T - 1$

$$\epsilon_{t,j} \sim p_\epsilon$$

4: **for** $t = T - 1, T - 2, \dots, 0$ **do**

5: Predict clean sample

$$\hat{x}_0^{(t)} = G(x_{t+1})$$

6: Construct the nested target mask

$$m_t = (r < p_t)$$

7: Construct the lower-corruption state

$$x_t = (1 - m_t) \odot \hat{x}_0^{(t)} + m_t \odot \epsilon_t$$

8: **end for**

9: Output $x_{\text{gen}} = x_0$

The sampling chain is nested in its mask pattern, because the same threshold field defines every m_t . It is not a value-carrying Markov chain for masked noise: coordinates that remain masked at the next lower level are assigned the level- t replacement noise ϵ_t , rather than copying their previous value from x_{t+1} . The reverse path is therefore

$$x_{t+1} \longrightarrow \hat{x}_0^{(t)} = G(x_{t+1}) \longrightarrow x_t = (1 - m_t) \odot \hat{x}_0^{(t)} + m_t \odot \epsilon_t.$$

Because $p_0 = 0$, the final target mask is $m_0 = 0$ and the final transition returns the clean prediction.

4 Relation to Gaussian Diffusion

4.1 Common corruption ratio

AMD and a Gaussian diffusion baseline can be compared by using the same scalar p_t as a common corruption ratio. In AMD, p_t is the marginal probability that a coordinate is replaced by noise. In Gaussian diffusion, we write

$$p_t = 1 - \bar{\alpha}_t,$$

so that p_t is the Gaussian noise-variance fraction and $1 - p_t$ is the signal-power fraction [2]. Both views use the endpoint convention

$$p_0 = 0, \quad p_T = 1.$$

The same scalar schedule therefore defines different corrupted states: AMD creates a mixture of exact clean coordinates and level-wise replacement-noise coordinates with a nested mask pattern, whereas Gaussian diffusion blends every coordinate with Gaussian noise.

The noise distributions are also different. AMD only requires a coordinate-wise replacement distribution p_ϵ . For images, a unit-variance example is $\mathcal{U}[-\sqrt{3}, \sqrt{3}]$. Gaussian diffusion instead uses coordinate-wise i.i.d. additive noise,

$$\epsilon_{t,j} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1).$$

For compactness, Table 1 writes the clean prediction as $\hat{x}_0 = G(x_{t+1})$ for both masked diffusion and the Gaussian-diffusion baselines. The table includes both marginal corrupted states and the path update used after a clean prediction, since both corruption families define reverse trajectories rather than isolated marginals only. In clean-marginal adversarial variants, the generator is timestep-free, and the discriminator network receives only clean-space samples; timestep dependence is represented by the corruption distribution and by selection of the discriminator timestep head.

Table 1: Masked diffusion and Gaussian diffusion under a common corruption ratio p_t . The comparison includes both the marginal corrupted state and the path update used after clean prediction.

Aspect	Masked diffusion	Gaussian diffusion
Marginal state	$r_j \sim \mathcal{U}[0, 1]$, $m_t = (r < p_t)$ $\epsilon_{t,j} \sim p_\epsilon$ $x_t = (1 - m_t) \odot x_0 + m_t \odot \epsilon_t$	$\bar{\alpha}_t = 1 - p_t$ $\epsilon_t \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I)$ $x_t = \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} x_0 + \sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \epsilon_t$
Path structure	shared threshold field r $m_t = (r < p_t)$, so $m_t \leq m_{t+1}$ nested visibility across reverse steps	Gaussian Markov path $q(x_{t+1} x_t) = \mathcal{N}(\sqrt{\alpha_{t+1}} x_t, \beta_{t+1} I)$ $\alpha_{t+1} = \bar{\alpha}_{t+1} / \bar{\alpha}_t$
Noise	level-wise replacement noise image example: $\mathcal{U}[-\sqrt{3}, \sqrt{3}]$	coordinate-wise Gaussian noise $\epsilon_{t,j} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$
Meaning of p_t	Marginal fraction of replaced coordinates	Noise variance $1 - \bar{\alpha}_t$
Coordinate state	Exact clean value or replacement noise	Attenuated clean value plus Gaussian noise
Clean prediction	$\hat{x}_0 = G(x_{t+1})$	$\hat{x}_0 = G(x_{t+1})$
Reverse update after \hat{x}_0	$x_t = (1 - m_t) \odot \hat{x}_0 + m_t \odot \epsilon_t$	$x_t \sim q(x_t x_{t+1}, \hat{x}_0)$
Regression loss	$L_{\text{path}} = \frac{1}{d_x} \ (1 - m_{t+1}) \odot (\hat{x}_0 - x_0)\ _2^2$	$L_{\text{Gauss}} = \frac{1 - p_{t+1}}{p_{t+1}} \frac{1}{d_x} \cdot \ \hat{x}_0 - x_0\ _2^2$

The Gaussian diffusion path signal assumes an x_0 -prediction model. Under Gaussian corruption,

$$x_{t+1} = \sqrt{1 - p_{t+1}} x_0 + \sqrt{p_{t+1}} \epsilon_{t+1},$$

the noise residual implied by an x_0 prediction is

$$\hat{\epsilon}_{t+1} - \epsilon_{t+1} = \sqrt{\frac{1 - p_{t+1}}{p_{t+1}}} (x_0 - G(x_{t+1})).$$

Thus the weighted x_0 -prediction MSE in Table 1 has the same scale as an ϵ -prediction MSE when a Gaussian regression term is enabled. The key difference is that AMD’s path loss, when used, applies MSE only to unmasked coordinates, while the standard Gaussian denoising regression signal is full-sample. In a clean-marginal adversarial model, enabling such a full-sample Gaussian regression term would make the adversarial loss and the regression loss both act on the full clean prediction. For small T , this can be unfavorable because the corrupted input admits multiple plausible completions, and the squared full-sample objective encourages a conditional-mean solution for ambiguous details. AMD instead uses MSE only as a path constraint on visible coordinates, so the adversarial loss remains responsible for distributional generation on masked coordinates.

4.2 Reverse update after clean prediction

The revised sampling/evaluation protocol differs between AMD and the Gaussian diffusion baseline because the two forward corruptions have different structure.

For AMD, after predicting $\hat{x}_0 = G(x_{t+1})$, the lower-corruption state is constructed with the nested target mask and a target-level replacement-noise draw:

$$m_t = (r < p_t), \quad \epsilon_{t,j} \sim p_\epsilon,$$

$$x_t = (1 - m_t) \odot \hat{x}_0 + m_t \odot \epsilon_t.$$

The mask threshold r is shared across the reverse chain, so the visibility pattern is nested. The replacement noise is not carried from x_{t+1} ; it is sampled separately for the target level t . This matches the implementation in which m_t is determined by a fixed threshold field while the noise tensor for each target level is stored separately.

For Gaussian diffusion, the corresponding Markov update is the posterior conditioned on the current state and the predicted clean sample. Let

$$\bar{\alpha}_t = 1 - p_t, \quad \alpha_{t+1} = \frac{\bar{\alpha}_{t+1}}{\bar{\alpha}_t} = \frac{1 - p_{t+1}}{1 - p_t}, \quad \beta_{t+1} = 1 - \alpha_{t+1}.$$

Then the Gaussian diffusion baseline samples

$$x_t = \mu_t^{\text{Gauss}}(x_{t+1}, \hat{x}_0) + \sigma_t z, \quad z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I),$$

where

$$\mu_t^{\text{Gauss}}(x_{t+1}, \hat{x}_0) = \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} \beta_{t+1}}{p_{t+1}} \hat{x}_0 + \frac{\sqrt{\alpha_{t+1}} p_t}{p_{t+1}} x_{t+1},$$

and

$$\sigma_t^2 = \frac{p_t}{p_{t+1}} \beta_{t+1}.$$

At $t = 0$, $p_0 = 0$, so $\sigma_0 = 0$ and the posterior mean reduces to \hat{x}_0 . This replaces the older independent Gaussian re-corruption rule with a state-conditioned Gaussian reverse step.

4.3 Schedules

Table 2 lists only example choices for the scalar schedule p_t . Once a schedule is chosen, the corresponding AMD and Gaussian corrupted states are obtained from Table 1. The cosine-style row is written under the corruption-ratio convention: Gaussian diffusion cosine schedules are often defined through the signal coefficient $\bar{\alpha}_t \propto \cos^2(\cdot)$; with zero offset and $p_t = 1 - \bar{\alpha}_t$, this corresponds to $p_t = \sin^2(\pi t / (2T))$ [6]. The log row uses an endpoint-forced convention: intermediate timesteps follow $1 - b^{t/T}$, and the endpoint is fixed to $p_T = 1$.

Table 2: Example schedules for the common corruption ratio p_t .

Schedule	Schedule function
Linear	$p_t = \frac{t}{T}$
Cosine-style	$p_t = \sin^2\left(\frac{\pi t}{2T}\right)$
Endpoint-forced log	$p_t = 1 - b^{t/T} \quad (t < T), \quad p_T = 1, \quad 0 < b < 1$

The same schedule can therefore define different learning problems. In AMD, p_t controls the marginal number of masked coordinates and, through the shared threshold field, the nested visibility pattern during sampling. In Gaussian diffusion, the same p_t controls the signal and noise coefficients through $\sqrt{1 - p_t}$ and $\sqrt{p_t}$. This is why the AMD path loss can be restricted to unmasked coordinates, whereas the Gaussian denoising signal is applied to the full sample.

5 Experiments

5.1 Dataset and implementation details

We evaluate the revised nested-mask, timestep-free-network version of AMD on CelebA-HQ images resized to 128×128 [7, 8]. Images have three channels and are represented in the range $[-\sqrt{3}, \sqrt{3}]$, matching the unit-variance uniform replacement-noise example used for masked diffusion. Unless otherwise stated, the schedule is linear with $T = 8$, the batch size is 16, and each run is trained for 100 epochs. The one-step GAN-equivalent masked-diffusion ablation uses $T = 1$; all other compared methods use $T = 8$. Samples are generated using an exponential moving average of the generator parameters with decay 0.999.

The generator is a timestep-free clean predictor: it receives the current corrupted state and predicts a clean sample. All explicit generator timestep conditioning is removed. In the AMD clean-marginal setting, the discriminator is always multi-head and receives only a clean-space sample: either a real x_0 or a generated clean prediction \hat{x}_0 . It returns a vector of timestep-head logits, and the sampled timestep only selects which head is used in the adversarial loss. Thus, timestep dependence is represented by the corruption level and by discriminator head selection, not by injecting a timestep embedding or corrupted conditioning state into either network.

For optimization, we use Adam [9] with

$$\text{lr}_D = 10^{-4}, \quad \text{lr}_G = 1.5 \times 10^{-4}, \quad \beta_1 = 0.5, \quad \beta_2 = 0.9.$$

The adversarial weight is 1.0, and the R1 regularization weight is 10.0. For masked diffusion, the no-path ablation disables the visible-coordinate path loss, while the AMD-equivalent setting uses $\lambda_{\text{path}} = 1$. For the Gaussian x_0 -marginal baseline, the path/regression term is the full-sample Gaussian x_0 -prediction loss

L_{Gauss} from Table 1. The conditional adversarial Gaussian baselines use no MSE loss.

5.2 Compared methods

The full comparison set is organized by corruption family and adversarial target. The default comparison uses $T = 8$, except for the one-step masked-diffusion GAN-equivalent ablation, which uses $T = 1$.

- **Masked diffusion, clean x_0 marginal adversarial (GAN-equivalent, $T = 1$).** This one-step ablation uses full replacement noise as the generator input. Since the visible-coordinate path loss is zero at $T = 1$, the model is equivalent to a GAN-style adversarial generator with image-shaped noise.
- **Masked diffusion, clean x_0 marginal adversarial, without L_{path} .** This is the masked-diffusion clean-marginal model with the path loss removed. It tests whether clean marginal adversarial learning alone is sufficient to make the generator use the corrupted input.
- **Masked diffusion, clean x_0 marginal adversarial, with L_{path} (AMD-equivalent).** This is the AMD-equivalent setting: masked diffusion with $T = 8$, clean x_0 marginal adversarial learning, nested-threshold masks, a timestep-free generator, a clean-input multi-head discriminator $D(u)$ whose selected head $D_t(u)$ supplies the adversarial logit, and the visible-coordinate path loss.
- **Gaussian diffusion, clean x_0 marginal adversarial.** This baseline replaces masked diffusion with Gaussian diffusion while keeping the clean x_0 marginal adversarial target. It uses the full-sample Gaussian x_0 -prediction path loss L_{Gauss} , and the lower-corruption state is sampled from the Gaussian posterior conditioned on the current state and the predicted clean sample.
- **Gaussian diffusion, conditional adversarial $x_t | x_{t+1}$ (DDGAN-equivalent).** This is the DDGAN-equivalent transition baseline. The discriminator receives either a real transition pair (x_t, x_{t+1}) or a generated transition pair (\hat{x}_t, x_{t+1}) , and no MSE loss is used.
- **Gaussian diffusion, conditional adversarial $x_0 | x_{t+1}$.** This conditional clean baseline uses Gaussian diffusion, but the discriminator receives a clean candidate together with the corrupted input: (x_0, x_{t+1}) for real samples and (\hat{x}_0, x_{t+1}) for generated samples. No MSE loss is used.

We use the term *Gaussian diffusion* rather than *DDPM diffusion* for these baselines because the comparison is defined by the Gaussian corruption family and posterior update, not by the full DDPM training recipe. The transition conditional baseline $x_t | x_{t+1}$ is the DDGAN-equivalent case, while $x_0 | x_{t+1}$ is a conditional clean adversarial variant.

5.3 Qualitative results

For readability, the qualitative section focuses on the AMD-equivalent setting rather than showing a separate figure for every baseline. We include two visualizations: a final sample grid and a reverse-path trace. The sample grid shows final generated images from the AMD-equivalent masked-diffusion model. The path trace shows how the same timestep-free generator produces clean predictions across the nested reverse chain.

Figure 1: Generated samples from the AMD-equivalent setting: masked diffusion with clean x_0 marginal adversarial learning and visible-coordinate path loss.

Figure 2: Reverse-path trace for the AMD-equivalent setting. The mask pattern follows a nested threshold field, while the generator is reused as the same timestep-free clean predictor at every reverse step.

5.4 Quantitative results

We report FID, precision, and recall. Lower FID is better, while higher precision and recall are better. Table 3 reports the completed CelebA-HQ 128×128 comparison. The GAN-equivalent masked-diffusion row is the only $T = 1$ result; every other row uses the default $T = 8$ setting. Table 4 reports the completed per-timestep diagnostic for the current masked-diffusion clean-marginal run.

Table 3: CelebA-HQ 128×128 comparison set. The table separates the corruption family, adversarial target, path/regression loss, and equivalent role. The GAN-equivalent masked-diffusion row uses $T = 1$; all other rows use the default $T = 8$.

Diffusion	Adversarial target	Path / reg. loss	Equivalent / role	FID ↓	Precision ↑	Recall ↑
Masked	x_0 marginal	none	GAN equiv. ($T = 1$)	19.9931	0.8041	0.0125
Masked	x_0 marginal	none	no-path ablation	17.2367	0.7184	0.1489
Masked	x_0 marginal	L_{path}	AMD equiv.	16.6109	0.7479	0.2011
Gaussian	x_0 marginal	L_{Gauss}	clean-marginal baseline	21.1357	0.7523	0.1254
Gaussian	$x_t x_{t+1}$ cond.	none	DDGAN equiv.	58.3376	0.6050	0.0003
Gaussian	$x_0 x_{t+1}$ cond.	none	conditional clean baseline	23.2990	0.8113	0.0583

Table 3 separates the main design axes in the comparison. The *Diffusion* column specifies whether the reverse chain is built from masked diffusion or Gaussian diffusion, the *Adversarial target* column specifies what the discriminator is asked to distinguish, and the *Path / reg. loss* column specifies the regression term used alongside the adversarial objective. The *Equivalent / role* column is placed immediately before the metrics so that each row can be read as a specific baseline or ablation before comparing performance. The proposed AMD-equivalent setting is the masked-diffusion, clean- x_0 -marginal adversarial model with L_{path} . It achieves the best overall FID and recall among the compared methods. Compared with the masked-diffusion clean-marginal model without L_{path} , enabling the path loss improves FID from 17.2367 to 16.6109 and recall from 0.1489 to 0.2011. Compared with the Gaussian diffusion clean-marginal baseline, which uses the full-sample Gaussian regression term L_{Gauss} , AMD improves FID from 21.1357 to 16.6109 and recall from 0.1254 to 0.2011. This suggests that, in this adversarial setting, masked diffusion with visible-coordinate path anchoring provides better coverage than the Gaussian full-sample regression baseline. The Gaussian conditional clean baseline $x_0 | x_{t+1}$ obtains the highest precision, but its recall is substantially lower, indicating a precision–coverage tradeoff. The Gaussian transition baseline $x_t | x_{t+1}$ is the DDGAN-equivalent setting and performs poorly in both FID and recall, supporting the motivation for keeping the adversarial discriminator on the clean marginal rather than on noisy transition pairs.

Table 4 reports the per-timestep x_0 -prediction evaluation. Each row evaluates the clean prediction $\hat{x}_0^{(t)}$ after a given number of reverse generator evaluations. The NFE column counts how many generator calls have been used from the fully corrupted initial state up to that prediction; therefore $t = 7$ corresponds to one NFE and $t = 0$ corresponds to eight NFEs.

Table 4: Per-timestep x_0 -prediction evaluation for the masked-diffusion clean-marginal run on CelebA-HQ 128×128 . NFE counts the number of generator evaluations from the start of the reverse chain.

Reverse step	NFE	t	p_{t+1}	FID ↓	Precision ↑	Recall ↑
0	1	7	1.000	18.0757	0.8347	0.1356
1	2	6	0.875	16.6929	0.8646	0.1939
2	3	5	0.750	16.7816	0.8705	0.1898
3	4	4	0.625	16.3570	0.8576	0.1978
4	5	3	0.500	15.8234	0.8395	0.2024
5	6	2	0.375	15.2854	0.8187	0.2093
6	7	1	0.250	15.1179	0.7901	0.2140
7	8	0	0.125	16.4199	0.7473	0.2027

The per-timestep diagnostic shows that the reverse chain improves substantially after the first prediction from the fully corrupted input. FID and recall generally improve through the middle and late stages of the chain, with the best FID and recall in this run appearing at NFE 7. The final NFE 8 prediction has lower precision and slightly lower recall than the NFE 7 prediction, so this table should be read as a trajectory diagnostic as well as a final-sample evaluation. Overall, the cross-method and per-timestep results support the path-generation decoupling view: the clean marginal adversarial objective provides distribution matching, while the visible-coordinate path loss improves coverage and stabilizes the multi-step masked reverse chain.

6 Conclusion

We introduced Adversarial Masked Diffusion, a generative modeling framework that separates reverse-path preservation from distribution learning. AMD uses nested coordinate-wise Bernoulli replacement masks to define corrupted inputs. The generator predicts a clean sample from the corrupted state without receiving an explicit timestep input, an unmasked-coordinate regression loss preserves the visible part of the input, and a timestep-free multi-head clean marginal discriminator supplies the distributional learning signal through timestep-head selection.

This separation clarifies the role of the two losses. Regression is not used as a full denoising objective over all coordinates; it is restricted to local path consistency. Adversarial learning is not asked to model noisy transition compatibility; it is kept on the clean data manifold. On CelebA-HQ 128×128 , the AMD-equivalent setting obtains the best FID and recall among the evaluated comparison set, and the per-timestep diagnostic shows how sample quality changes along the nested reverse chain.

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